

doi:10.5281/zenodo.20060232

Evaluation of the Contributions of Parents Teachers Associations in the Administration of Public Secondary School in Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

In different secondary schools in Anambra state, there is the existence of Parents Teachers' Association (PTA) which is believed, helps the school administration in ensuring both the infrastructural and academic growth of the school. This study examined the contribution of Parents Teachers' Association in secondary school administration in Anambra state public schools. The objective is to know if PTAs actually help in the administration of the schools, the areas where they assist the school administration, the position of the school authorities in the involvement of PTAs and the nature of assistance offered by PTAs. Based on the objectives, four research questions guided the study. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The research is anchored on the classical administrative theory, human relations theory and the systems theory. The population of the study is 263 school principals in Anambra state education zones. The researcher adopted a census study. A 32-item questionnaire was developed and used for data collection from the principals. Data collected were analyzed with the aid of means and standard deviation for the research questions. Finding of the study showed that the PTA helps in school-community relationship, raising funds, discipline and providing security in the schools. Based on these findings, the study recommends among others that teachers and the PTA should see themselves as partners in the process of educating the children. Government should provide guidelines for PTA operations for them to know their limits. Also, the government should monitor the operations of the PTA and ensure that only men and women of integrity are appointed to run the affairs of the association.

Keywords: Government, Secondary schools, Parents Teachers Association, Contribution, Administration

INTRODUCTION

Immediately after birth, parents especially the mother starts to pass information to a child. This continues until the child is of age and is enrolled into a school. Even while in school when the child in the care of teachers, parents monitor their activities to ensure that they are given the best training they deserved. This is because all parents have the natural inclination to give their children the good things of life including education. In the modern age, the major task is on the provision of quality education and good standard of living. In the light of this, parents have developed a very positive interest in what goes on in school. It is this interest of parents in the education of their children and wards in schools that gave birth to the organization or formation of the "Parents-Teachers' Association."

The Parents-Teachers' Association is a voluntary and welfare Association of Parents and Guardians, as well as teachers of a particular school. In some countries this association of parents and teachers is called by other names, irrespective of whatever name it is known in different countries, the objectives of Parents-Teachers' Association (P.T.A.) is essentially the same. During the later years of the 19th century, the Parents-Teachers' Association was first organized by a group of women in America. The first meeting called "the national congress of mothers" was actually held in 1877. It was this meeting that stimulated the founding of the national congress of parents and teachers in association in 2000.

The congress of parents and teachers, which now goes by the name Parents-Teachers' Association {PTA} and the functions, now includes particularly in curricular development policy making and setting standards in schools. After the government takeover of schools, the then East Central State Government saw the need for the involvement of the community especially the Parents-Teachers' Association in the administration of Schools. It saw that it was obvious that government alone cannot cater for the education of the children, and that there is the need to involve the Parents-Teachers' Association. The children, belong to the Parents who are the PTA, therefore, the education of the children is important to them too, it is a collective responsibility. Government plays its role, and parents including teachers, play their own role in the education of the children. Ezeocha, (1990), defined the Parents-Teachers' Association as a voluntary and welfare association of parents/ guardians of children of a particular school with the teachers who teach in that school as members. Parents-Teachers' Association also helps to promote an understanding between the home and the school, which is between the teachers, the parents and the student. Ukeje, (1992), sees Parents-Teachers' Association as a formal establishment that comprises parents whose children are currently registered as students in a school with teachers in that school. From the definitions, we see that though parents sometimes are not really the official teachers of their children, they play an important role in the training of their children both at home and in the school; because they serve as a link between what happens at home and what happens in the school environment.

This relationship between the school and the home helps to instill discipline in children, since a child would know that his activities both at home and in school can be monitored and communicated to either the school or the home. To Ohuche and Ali, (1989), the purpose of the Parents-Teachers' Association is to bring the home and the school close to each other, to study the problem of the children and if possible find solutions that are mutually beneficial.

According to Elui (2007), the aim of P.T.A. is to enable parents know what is going on in the school and also give their opinion on certain issues concerning children. The P.T.A. finances capital projects like construction of new administrative or classroom block, fencing of the school, provision of staff quarters, staff rooms, laboratories, etc. She went further to say that through P.T.A., parents and teachers interact and take decisions on the management and welfare of the children, teachers and the school.

Oboegbulem (2004) said that "the teachers' devotion to duty build up the status of the school community. The report card's on students' learning progress in school allows for indirect communication between the teachers and the parents and should be recognized as a valuable tool for improvement of public relations". So we see directly or indirectly the teacher is a link between the parents and the children who they are responsible for while in school. It's a triangle from parents at home to teachers in school and back home. This should establish a more direct relationship between the teachers and the parents that is between the home and the school. Their responsibility to the children should be seen as a joint relationship. The PTA as" playing a mediatory function, to bring about smooth teacher/student relationship, while improving quality education and good character of students. PTA should be there to encourage students to learn not only to respect school authorities but also to trust their teachers' ability to mold them into responsible citizens.

The association was first started in the United States of America by a group of parents (mothers) who were concerned about the welfare of the children. "Charity kindergartens or so-called free kindergartens for children of the poor became one of the main instruments of the progressive women's and social movements of the late 1880s and 1890s. Some of these schools were parts of settlement houses, such as Hull House in Chicago, established by American social reformer Jane Addams. The teachers from these

charity kindergartens often made home visits and taught songs and games to mothers to use with their children. These meetings between parents and kindergarten teachers eventually helped lead to the founding of the National Congress of Parents and Teachers, also known as the Parents-Teachers' Association (PTA)". Microsoft Encarta (2007).

According to Mgbodile (1986), this association started by Alice Birney and Pheobe Heart as National Congress of Mothers. Later in 1924, became known as "National Congress of Parents and Teachers" had as its main objective as:

- To promote child welfare in home, school, church and community, to raise the standards of home life, to secure more adequate Laws for the care and protection of the children.
- To bring close relations between home and school that parents and teachers may co-operate intelligently in the training of the child and to develop a united effort in order to ensure moral and spiritual training.

The Parent's Teachers Association's stated mission is to support and speak on behalf of children and youths in schools and in the community, and before governmental agencies and other organizations whose decisions affect children; to assist parents in developing the skills they need to raise and protect their children; and to encourage parental and public involvement in schools. Though the Parent- Teachers Association (PTA) was started by parents the need for teachers to be involved in it was seen hence the inclusion of teachers in the association.

If the school is to achieve its goal, meet the needs of students and fulfill the expectation of parents, there should be good linkage between the teachers and parents. Parents are experienced people who are conversant with child psychology and development. They therefore know the needs of their children at difference stages of development. In view of this, the parents are in a better position to give useful advice to teachers when necessary. Individual parents could be invited to school for discussion on their children welfare. The principal with the assistance of the staff points at the children weakness and give suggestion for improvement. The parent's teacher association is a forum for teachers and parents to meet and discuss issues relating to the welfare of the parents and teachers. Through the PTA meeting, parents could be educated or enlightened on the discipline and causes of students' delinquency. Through this the parents will have an insight into the causes of the student's problem and understand more effective ways of dealing with such problem. He will also know the danger associated with ineffective discipline.

Iwuanwu (2006) opined that teachers on the other hand are made to accept the fact that parents have not only a duty, but also a right to take active part in discussing and taking decision on all the facts or aspects of the education of their children. In fact, the effect of a good organized and effective parent-teachers association is to make both parents and teachers alike to (a) want to understand more about the children that are being educated so as to be in a better position to help them move effectively (b) appreciate the necessity for constant dialogue and communication between parents and teachers and hence the need to create a system or channel through which it will take place; (c) realize that the two parties are equally important in the education process of the children and that the educational objectives we have for these children will not be achieved without both parties playing active role.

From the above it is seen that the role of the Parents Teachers Association (P.T.A) in the administration and management of schools is much, ranging from showing interest and concern in the affairs of the school which includes discipline, serving as a link between the school and the community, to assisting the school in the moral upbringing of the students and helping the school financially through fund raising and building of infrastructures. The awareness of these facts has necessitated the need for P.T.A's full support and therefore the need for modalities to improve the participation of P.T.A in the administration of secondary schools.

There is need to have a community relations unit established in schools, by the P.T .A, to help create a link between the school and the community they reside in. Communities sometimes are hostile and quarrel with some of the activities of the schools, if such a unit exists, they will mediate between the school and the community, and also acquaint the communities with some of the activities the school plans

to engage in that could affect the community directly or indirectly. Non establishment of community relations unit of Parents Teachers Association as a link between the school and the community is a serious omission in the edict establishing the P.T.A in the school. While Ojelabi (1981) observed that it is the involvement of the community in education that makes the system worthwhile. Schools reside in communities and if these communities are not made to take active part in the school activities then the school cannot integrate with the community neither would the community be able to appreciate how nor where help could be rendered to the school. It is said that “*no man is an island*” both have to complement each other for their mutual benefit.

There is need for the school to get the community and the PTA involved in school activities, like bazaars, carols, open day, such activities that would make the community come to the school and participate in the life of the students at school. And apart from the school generating some revenue from these, it creates a bond between the two. A bond that would make it easier to deal with problems when they arise, problems do arise in relationships, it could be non-cooperation and exertion of undue influence by the PTA. Some member might want a student promoted to a higher class because of who the parent is in the society, some might try to use their political and personal influence to appoint principals or teachers even when they are not qualified, even interference from the school management boards through influential Parents Teachers Association members.

These are inherent problems but such is human nature. P.T.A can participate actively in the administration of schools through involving them in administrative decision making processes. P.T.A executives being invited to the school to participate when decisions are being taken in school, regarding matters that affect students directly, like punishments to be given about delinquency, late coming, absenteeism etc. Policy decisions that would help curb indiscipline. Indiscipline in schools is a common feature, more common in public schools than in private ones. But with active participation of the Parents Teachers Association (P.T.A) it could be curbed. In private schools, the code of conduct is set and both parents and students are made aware of it even before admission and the implications of breaking any of them.

Problems abound that the school might not really know about, getting the PTA involved in the problems of the school will make them know about them and proffer solutions. Apart from discipline there are other numerous problems a school encounter, problems funds provided by the PTA could help to solve, or donations or services by some members that cannot provide money could solve.

Members who are carpenters take it upon themselves to effect necessary repairs to school furniture, damaged windows and doors, leaking roofs, rotten ceiling boards and sagging ceiling. Members who are plumbers reactivate dry water taps, or arrange for the dislodgment of septic tanks, and those who are painters give the school buildings occasional face lifts, building material sellers donate such materials, building contractors carry out minor and major repair jobs to put school buildings in good shape, flooded or water-logged areas of the school premises can be sand filled and or drained, broken fences mended. Those who are traders can supply the school with materials like plastic bowls, buckets, refuse bins, hand towels and cleaning materials. During school activities, some female members could accept the responsibility for the provision of light refreshment, provision of simple books and other materials for prize-giving ceremonies, sport competitions and even donation of trophies for sports tournaments. Those in the information communication technology (ICT) industry donate equipment they sell; these would remove the burden on some members who might not have cash readily. Though all these are however, subject to the approval of the relevant school management committee and the ministry of education.

Members of the PTA can also make arrangements for recreation during school holidays, that is, excursion to industries, factories, museums and other places of interest, as well as, offering of guidance and counseling services in the parents' own areas of strength. Experts in other vital areas can be invited to deliver lectures on various careers; parents could also help in organizing short talks on sex education, moral responsibilities, obedience to authority and compliance with the laws of the land.

Government, because of so many irregularities in the handling of funds and the misuse of such funds by the people that handle them, no longer encourage the imposition of levies rather it is now encouraging the P.T.A to make contributions. Government now insists that P.T.A's money should be handled and

disbursed by the P.T.A.. The P.T.A should now make contributions to provide such facilities like school bus for easy transportation of students from school to places they need to go to, like for school debates, the stadium for sports or children's day celebrations, field trips or on excursions. Ambulances for emergencies to hospitals, water tankers where there are no water or boreholes for the students paying for P.T.A teachers which they now employ to alleviate the problem of inadequate number of teachers and even buildings can be donated to schools through the P.T.A. these are to alleviate some of the problems the school have which would otherwise have affected the smooth running of the school and effective teaching and learning.

Teachers are also parents and part of the P.T.A. They have the most crucial and active part to play in the effectiveness of the role of the association; They will, welcome the assistance from parents once they have accepted the initial idea of parents helping in a really practical manner. Teachers will then see parents as partners in progress in the education of the children because a great demand is made on parents, for instance, raising funds to supplement equipment is of course, an important part of parental involvement, especially at this time of high cost of living in Nigeria. If teachers give their full cooperation and support, there would be mutual understanding and a better working environment all round. The P.T.A is poised to do everything in their power to move education to a greater height.

Prior to the Nigeria-Biafran civil war, most of the schools were owned and managed by different Christian missionary bodies as well as private individuals. In fact, in the area that is now known as Anambra State, the government did not own any post-primary institution. Before the civil war, almost all the schools both primary and secondary as well as teachers training institutions were owned by the missionaries and some philanthropic individuals who were responsible for the appointment, discipline, promotion as well as termination of teachers. The school proprietors received grants-in-aid from the government to help them in the running of schools. Another source of revenue available to school proprietors were fees of different types which were charged to the pupils. With the money realized from all these sources, they paid the teachers, equipped the school and defrayed other sundry expenses incurred in the day to day running of the schools, Okeke (2004). *Journal of Teacher Perspective*. The State Ministry of Education concentrated on the maintenance of standards in terms of curriculum and the school structure.

The quest to investigate the importance of parents in the administration and development of secondary school and the need for parents-teachers co-operation motivated the researcher to carry on with this research work.

Statement of the Problem

The Parent-Teachers-Association has already become part of the present school system but the degree of its usefulness is largely dependent on how far individual administration uses it. This fact is recognized when it is stated in the Anambra handbook on school Administration that "PTA can be a useful arm of the school administration depending on how well it co-operates with the Principal and staff in its vital role which should be to act as a link between the school and the home in solving problems of personality, finance and general conduct of the pupils/student. Parents as individuals should be listened to, each time they bring up a complaint and the school side of the matter should be presented clearly to them.

The educational performance of Nigerian/Students and standard of education in Nigeria seem to be gradually falling thus leading to the question as to the role of the parents' teachers' association in the administration of schools in Nigeria. There is also a growing concern over the poor performance of students in the just released WASSCE examinations thus leading to this study in examining the role of this PTA in improving this decline. Do parents teachers association help in improving the general administration of schools in Nigeria? Are their inputs as stakeholders required of them to improve the seemingly declining education sector? All these are the problems that led to the conduct of this study.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to evaluate the effectiveness of PTA as a stakeholder in secondary school administration in Anambra State.

Specifically, the study sets out to:

Evaluate the effectiveness of the P.T.A. in fund raising in the secondary school administration.

- Assess the contributions made by the PTA in the development, promotion of discipline and decision making among the students, teachers and management officials.
- Evaluate how the co-operation between principals/staff and parents can improve the execution of projects in the school.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. How does PTA discharge their duties in the area of fund raising in running of secondary schools?
2. What are the contributions made by the PTA in promoting discipline in the secondary schools?
3. How can the co-operation between principals, staff and parents improve the execution of projects in the school?

Research Hypotheses

H₀: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of the PTA in fund raising in running of the school.

H₀: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of the PTA in promoting discipline and execution of projects in secondary schools in Anambra state.

Scope of the Study

This study focuses on the secondary schools in the six education zones in Anambra state. The study will evaluate the effectiveness of PTA in the improving administration in secondary schools in Anambra state and the contribution/co-operation improvement of the school system. The six educational zones to be used are Aguata, Awka, Nnewi, Ogidi, Onitsha and Otuocha. There are 257 public secondary schools under the above listed zones at present.

Conceptual Clarifications

Parents Teachers Association is one of the agencies of the community which supports school administration. According to Oboegbulem and Onwurah (2011), Parent – Teacher Association (PTA) is one of the strongest agencies of the community that influences school administration. According to the Anambra state regulation for the parent-teacher association section 18 (sub-section 6). A parent-teacher association is a voluntary and welfare association of parents/guardians of children of a particular school with the teachers who teach in that school as members. It is an association which promotes mutual understanding and co-operation between the school and the home. The P.T.A. provides an opportunity for both teachers and parents to meet together to discuss matter affecting the school. The researcher sees PTA as a body or organization that enables parents know what is going on in the school, give their support in promotion and development when need arise and also give their opinion on certain issues concerning children.

The main aim of forming the parents-teachers association varies from one place to another and from one school to the other depending on the initiative of the founders and the immediate need for the formation.

In this case, the aim of forming a parents-teachers' association is to look into the affairs of the pupils and students to ensure the free and fair running of the school which will determine the general behaviour of the students.

It is equally an opportunity for both parents and teachers to meet together to resolve matters affecting the schools and the students respectively. Most of the problems that would have hindered the effective guidance and learning of the students both at school and at home are easily resolved by this association.

Over the years, the PTA has recorded a great achievement in administration of school community relationship. It is wise to say that there is nothing that has advantage without disadvantages. In spite of all the recorded achievement and contributions of PTA yet it is true that there are problems associated with the PTA in secondary school administration in Anambra State. It must however, be noted that these problems emanated as a result of lack of influence in school community relationship on the side of the teachers. Some parents want teachers only to help in the instruction of subject and normal training of their children and no more. Other important problems encountered by the parents teacher association are: Lack of funds

and the inability of parent to respond to invitations of meeting. Very many high percentages of parents do not care to attend the association meeting. The presence of such meetings could have gone a long way to encourage the smooth running of the day-to-day activities of the school.

Theoretical Framework

This work is anchored on three theories. These are, the classical administrative theory, human relations theory and the system theory.

Scientific/Classical Administration Theory

Classical administrative theory an early form of organization theory, pioneered mainly by Henri Fayol (1841–1925), which was concerned principally with achieving the ‘most rational’ organization for coordinating the various tasks specified within a complex division of labor. Fayol is regarded as the first to question the nature of management and put forward a theory designed to apply in all managerial contexts.

Classical administrative theory, like its near-contemporary the scientific management approach, rests on the premise that organizations are unproblematically rational and (effectively) closed systems. In other words, organizations are assumed to have unambiguous and unitary objectives, which the individuals within them pursue routinely, by obeying the rules and fulfilling their role expectations, according to the prescribed blueprint and structure. Moreover, in the attempt to maximize efficiency, it is only variables within that structure that need to be considered and manipulated. The interaction of the organization with its environment, together with the various factors which are external to the organization but nevertheless have consequences for its internal functioning, are systematically ignored. Fayol attempted to present his theory in such a way that the business procedures he had studied and developed as managing director of a mining and metallurgical company in France could be applied to any organization, regardless of size or nature. He proposed that managerial activity should involve five major elements: forecasting and planning; organizing; commanding; coordinating; and controlling. His ideas remained influential for much of the 20th century. (Microsoft ® Encarta 2007) The theory emphasized productivity; it did not really bother about the human elements, but in what they can achieve. Here the objective is for work to be done and achieved with the lowest possible cost, worker's interest and aspirations were completely ignored and suppressed. A scientific management type of manager, is the one who tries to avoid any human contact with his staff and treats them as economically motivated automatons. According to Unachukwu, The classical principles are very important to the organizer since their knowledge will help him tackle some problems relating to assignment of functions to departments and individuals, means of coordinating efforts, grouping of work to be done, etc. The classical theory has been criticized as being too broad in terms of implementation by the organizer. (Unachukwu, 2004).

The relevance of this theory to this work might seem strange, but an administrator can apply it to, minimize cost, and still achieve a good result. The administrator can get the PTA, the teachers and even the students to appreciate that what they all are aspiring to achieve at the end of the term is the best result in an external examination. The parents could donate materials to enhance teaching and learning, the teachers put on extra hours without anticipating any monetary reward and students study extra hard, in order not to disappoint the teachers and their parents that are already sacrificing so much for them.

Human Relations Theory of Administration

Human relations theory (HRT) is normally thought of as having its roots in the Hawthorne Studies conducted in the 1920s and 1930s at the Hawthorne works of the Western Electric Company, near Chicago in the United States. Human relations theory is used to structure understandings of organizations, especially on the part of their managers and so now human relations theory begins to take on a very different aspect. In one way, it is a response to the failure, or at least limitations, of scientific management as a means of organizational control. But it is a response which in many ways offers not an alternative to, but an extension of, scientific management. What I mean to say is that human relations theory bears the same footprint of formal or instrumental rationality as that to be found in scientific management. Human relations theory tries to understand the problems and anxieties of her staff and to encourage their wider

motivations to work. The school administrator applying this theory, would make the PTA understand that, the teachers, and students when encouraged and motivated would give their maximum. When people are treated humanly the tendency is for them to respond positively, in this case, the administrator get the best of the staff and students alike.

Systems Theory

This is an interdisciplinary field of science and the study of the nature of complex systems in nature, society, and science. It is a framework by which one can analyze and/or describe any group of objects that work in concert to produce some result. This could be a single organism, any organization or society. Systems theory first originated in biology in the 1920s out of the need to explain the interrelatedness of organisms in ecosystems. It is believed that all organisms as well as human organizations are systems, they are not static but rather grow, and they are maintained and improved on. Administrative theorists view organization, as well as educational organizations as a social system of interrelated parts, believing that the only way to study an organization is to study it as a system; that is a total system, where the environment, the formal arrangements, the total system, the technical systems are all interacting. Nwankwo, (1982) defined a system as a unit with a series of inter related and interdependent parts, such that the interplay of any part, affects the whole e.g in the education sub systems, primary, secondary and tertiary are inter related. Since the system is an inter related part, and the human organisms in it a part of the social system, and all interplay and this interplay affect each other. It could rightly be observed that any decisions taken for the child at the primary level of education is likely to affect the child either negatively or positively as he/she goes on. A good foundation laid for the child then will help him/her get along.

METHODOLOGY

This work adopted the descriptive survey design. The design enables the researcher collect data on the effectiveness of the duties of PTA as a stakeholder in the administration of secondary school. Osegbo, Ifeakor and Enemu (2009), described survey design as the investigator's attempt to gather data from a portion of a population for the purpose of examining the characteristics, opinions, or intentions of that population.

The study took place conducted in the six education zones in Anambra State of Nigeria namely Aguata, Awka, Nnewi, Ogidi, Onitsha and Otuocha. There are a total of 256 public secondary schools in Anambra state. (Planning, Research and Statistics Department, Ministry of Education Awka, 2025).

The population comprised the Senior Secondary (SS) students in the six education zones of Anambra State. There are 51, 217 SS students in the zone. 7316 in Aguata zone, 11554 in Awka zone, 7487 in Nnewi zone, 7481 in Ogidi zone, 14,992 in Onitsha zone and 2387 in Otuocha zone. These made up a total of 51, 217 SS students in education zone of Anambra public school.

The sample consists of 382 respondents drawn from the population in accordance with the Krejcie and Morgan's Table of sample size determination. The respondents were selected using simple random sampling technique. Two (2) Schools were selected from each of the education zones, 31 respondents (students) were selected to represent each school. When this 31 is multiplied by 12 selected school, it gives a total of 382 as population of the study.

A questionnaire was used as the instrument for data collection. The questionnaire is made up of two parts A and B. Part A was personal data while part B contained items on the effectiveness of the duties of PTA as a stakeholder in administration of secondary school. The items were structured on four-point scale of Strongly Agree, Agree, disagree and Strongly Agree.

The copies of questionnaire will be distributed on the sampled respondents which is 382 in their different schools with the help of three trained research assistants. Arrangements will be made with all the principals on how to reach the students for the instrument to be administered on a meeting day and collected same day.

Method of Data Analysis

Mean rating and standard deviation will be used in answering the research questions. The midpoint for four-point rating scale which is 2.5 will be used as agreement level of the items. Items with mean ratings of 2.5 and above will be accepted while items with mean ratings below 2.49 will be rejected.

PRESENTATION OF DATA

This section presents the data by giving demographic information of the sample under study. The frequencies and percentages are shown in Table I.

Table I: Demographic information of the sample

Categories	Level	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	61	39
	Female	92	61
Location	Urban	109	69
	Rural	48	31

Source: Field survey, 2026

Table 1 showed that the sample consisted of 61 (39%) males and 96 (61%) female. Distribution according to location was urban 109 (69%) and rural 48 (31%). Data obtained were analysed using descriptive statistic by computing mean and standard deviation.

Research Question 1: *What are the contributions made by the PTA in promoting school-community relationship in secondary school?*

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of PTA in promoting school-community relationship

S/N	Item description	N	X	SD
1	PTA represents the interest of the parents and guardian	157	3.25	0.60
2	PTA bridges the gap between the school and community	157	3.07	0.43
3	PTA motivates both teachers and students	157	3.15	0.64
4	PTA provides basic amenities	157	3.29	0.69
5	PTA promotes the development of schools	157	3.36	0.63
6	PTA promotes connection with mgt	157	3.33	0.66
7	PTA establish...	157	3.11	0.73
8	PTA helps in promote academic excellence	157	3.20	0.67

Source: Field survey, 2026

The result in table 2 indicated that the mean scores of the respondents on contributions made by PTA in promoting school-community relationship in secondary school of Anambra State ranged from 3.07 to 3.36. The result implied that PTA contributed greatly to the promotion of school-community relationship as can be seen from the mean responses.

Research Question 2: *How does PTA discharge its duties in the area of fund raising for school projects?*

Table 3: Mean and SD of PTA on fund raising for school projects

S/N	Item description	N	X	SD
9	PTA levy itself or sch dev	157	3.43	0.54
10	PTA contribute to mgt deision	157	3.16	0.55
11	PTA help in walling of schools	157	2.96	0.51
12	PTA partner with schools	157	3.44	0.60
13	PTA help in infrastructure dev.	157	3.22	0.71
14	PTA help in the purchase	157	3.42	0.70
15	PTA help in curriculum dev.	157	3.14	0.52
16	PTA attract individual donors	157	3.17	0.69

Source: Field survey, 2026

Table 3 showed the mean scores and standard deviation of how PTA helps on fund raising for school projects. The result revealed that they make extremely energetic effort to the funding of school projects. This is shown by the mean responses of the respondents ranging from 2.96 to 3.44 which signified positive involvement.

Research Question 3: *To what extent does PTA contribute its quota in the area of school discipline and management?*

Table 4: Mean and SD of PTA contribution to school discipline and management

S/N	Item description	N	X	SD
17	PTA help in settling disputes	157	2.94	0.48
18	Management liaise with PTA in taking...	157	2.70	0.60
19	PTA involves itself in sch dev.	157	2.70	0.72
20	PTA partner with management	157	2.96	0.77
21	PTA involves in organizing	157	2.87	0.77
22	PTA cooperates with mgt.	157	3.08	0.71

Source: Field survey, 2026

Table 4 revealed the contribution of PTA to school discipline and management. They collaborate with school management to maintain order and discipline in the school. They are also involved in the management of vital areas in the school. This was indicated by their responses to the item statements.

Test of Hypotheses

Three null hypotheses were tested with independent t-test at .05 alpha level.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female PTA in promoting school-community relationship in the secondary school.

Table 5: Independent t-test analysis of male and female PTA in promoting school- community relationship

Variation	N		SD	t-calc.	Df	t-crit.
Male	61	25.52	3.27	1.152*	155	1.96
Female	96	25.96	1.51			

*not significant at $P < .05$, $df = 155$

Table 5 showed independent t-test analysis of male and female PTA in promoting school-community relationship. The calculated t-value (1.152) at 155 degree of freedom and .05 level of significant was less than the critical t-value (1.96). based on the result, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between male and female PTA in promoting school-community relationship is not rejected. Hence, there is no significant difference between male and female PTA in promoting school-community relationship.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of urban and rural PTA in the area of fund raising for school projects

Table 6: Independent t-test analysis of urban and rural PTA on fund raising for school projects

Variation	N		SD	t-calc.	Df	t-crit.
Urban	109	25.71	2.68	.798*	155	1.96
Rural	48	26.04	1.35			

*not significant at $P < .05$, $df = 155$

From table 6, it was found out that the calculated t-value (.798) was less than the critical t-value (1.96) at .05 level of significance and 155 degrees of freedom. This indicated that the null hypothesis was failed to reject hence retained. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the mean scores of urban and rural PTA on fund raising for school projects.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female PTA on discipline and management of schools

Table 7: Independent t-test of male and female PTA on discipline and management of schools

Variation	N		SD	t-calc.	Df	t-crit.
Male	61	17.52	2.24	1.363*	155	1.96
Female	96	17.10	1.61			

*not significant at $P < .05$, $df = 155$

From table 7, it was revealed that the calculated t-value (1.363) was less than the critical t-value of 1.96 at .05 alpha level and 155 degrees of freedom. This implied that the null hypothesis of no significant difference between male and female PTA on discipline and management was not rejected. Hence, there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female PTA on discipline and management. Any difference could be attributed to chance.

Summary of the Findings

From the analysis of the data, the following summary was put forward;

- There is no significant difference between the male and female PTA in promoting school-community relationship.
- There is no significant difference between urban and rural PTA on fund raising for school projects.
- There is no significant difference between male and female PTA on discipline and management. Any difference could be attributed to chance

To find answer to the three research questions, 157 copies of questionnaire were distributed to the male and female principals selected from the sample frame. Their responses showed that the PTA contribute effectively to the administration of secondary schools in Anambra State.

To ascertain whether the research questions are positive or negative, a research hypothesis was tested with independent t-test at .05 alpha level. Data obtained from the study were analysed using appropriate statistical tools. The tools include frequencies and percentages, mean and standard deviation.

The human relation theory of administration, classical administration theory and system theory. To address the research objectives, literature relevant to the study were reviewed. Relevant literature from other researchers showed that PTA has shown a high level of effectiveness in administration of secondary schools.

The evaluative research method was used in the execution of the study. That is, the researcher employed both the qualitative and quantitative research methods. Using the Krejcie and Morgan's table size distribution, a sample of 157 respondents was selected from the population of 257.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The quest to investigate the importance of parents in the administration and development of secondary school in Anambra State and the need for parents-teachers co-operation motivated the researcher to carry out this research work.

The study focused on the evaluation of effectiveness of the duties of PTA in administration of secondary schools in Anambra State. the major interest in the study was to determine whether there is any contributions made by the PTA in promoting school-community relationship in the secondary school; to find out how PTA discharges its duties in the area of fund raising for school projects, and also to find out how PTA contributes its quota in the area of students' discipline and school management. The findings showed that PTA makes a great contribution in the administration of secondary schools in Anambra state.

CONCLUSION

The effectiveness of the duties of PTA in the administration of secondary schools cannot be over-emphasized. They help in promoting school community relations thereby bringing the community to know what is happening in the school and also to promote the affairs and activities of the school. They help in fund raising for infrastructural development, making rules for discipline, catering for students welfare and making of decisions. They also help in resource management with regards to finance and school property.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the finding and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations are made.

1. The government should formally recognize PTA as partners with school administrations in the development of secondary schools in different parts of the state.

2. Government should also involve the association in the infrastructural developments in schools especially in monitoring projects. This is necessary because it is their wards that make use of these projects and they are closer to the schools.
3. The government should change the mindset of members of the association and tell them that they are important partner and not only needed when the schools needs money for development.
4. The organization should appoint men of proven intergrity to handle the money contributed by the members of the association to avoid misappropriation of such funds.

REFERENCES

- Abdullahi, S. U. (1996). Parents teachers association as an instrument of community participation in education. <http://zealang.org/agulectures/eth>. Retrieved 31/03/2016.
- Elui, E. P. (2007). Home school and neighbourhood partnership in the education of the Nigerian child. A paper presented at the annual conference of journal of childhood and primary education. 3 (1). 111-120.
- Eze, S. (2008) Nigeria: Unity schools and the PTA politics, Web Posted Article
- Ezeocha, P. A. (1985). *School management and supervision*. Owerri: New African Publishing.
- Iwuanyanwu, S. I. C. (2006). The role of the teachers in the school setting. In E. J. Maduwesi and P. E. Eya (eds.). *Perspectives in teacher education*. Onitsha: West and Solomon Publishing Company Limited.
- Mgbodile, T. O. (1986). *Educational administration and supervision*. Heinemann Education Books (Nig) Ltd.
- Microsoft ® Encarta ® 2007. © 1993-2006 Microsoft Corporation. All rights reserved.
- Osegbo, I. E; Ifeakor, A. C. and Enemu, J. O. (2009). *Research methodology in education: basic issues and techniques*. Onitsha: Folmech Printing and Publishing Company Limited.
- Ukeje, B.O. (1992) (ed.) *Educational administration and planning*, Optimal Computers Solution Ltd. Nsukk